

NOVASOIL

INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH

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Report on second round of multiplier event

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Contributors	ALL

QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCEDURES

This document has been reviewed by the NOVASOIL consortium according to the national reports and comments received

TABLE REVISION HISTORY DELIVERABLE

Row	Version	Date	Reviewers	Description
1	V1.0	24/03/2025	EVENOR	Guideline approved and templates
2	V1.1	27/09/2023	ALL	Version updated based on inputs received
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Project Consortium

N°	Participant organisation name	Country
1	EVENOR TECH SLU	ES
2	LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG	GE
3	ZEMNIEKU SAEIMA	LV
4	NEW BULGARIAN UNIVERSITY	BU
5	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
6	KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	DK
7	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	GE
8	ASSEMBLEE DES REGIONS EUROPEENNES FRUITIERES LEGUMIERES ET HORTICOLES	FR
9	ISTITUTO DELTA ECOLOGIA APPLICATA SRL	IT
10	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA	IT
11	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	NL
12	CENTRE OF ESTONIAN RURAL RESEARCH AND KNOWLEDGE	EE
13	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	ES
14	UNIVERSITA DI PISA	IT
15	ASOCIACION AGRARIA JOVENES AGRICULTORES DE SEVILLA	ES
16	UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	GB

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1 List of Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
ME	Multiplier event
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
CoP	Community of Practice
SDGS30	Sustainable Development Goals 2030
EU	European Union
CS	Case Study
DoA	Description of Action
ES	Ecosystem Services
DST	Decision Support Tool
CN	Carbon Neutral

2 Executive summary

This document reports on activities carried out under task 5.4 (Multiplier events) in the framework of WP5 (Building a Community of Practice and dissemination strategy) of the NOVASOIL project.

The deliverable provides an overview of the second and final series of multiplier events organised by NOVASOIL partners during 2025. These events followed the initial round held in 2023 and aimed to consolidate stakeholder engagement, validate project results, and collect final feedback on NOVASOIL's business models, tools, and policy recommendations.

Compared to the first round, the second series focused more strongly on testing the applicability and usability of NOVASOIL outputs, including the Knowledge-Hub, Decision Support Tool (DST), Incentive Evaluation Tool, and the policy briefs developed in previous WPs.

The events integrated into this report involved over 100 participants across research, farming, seed production, advisory services, and policy sectors. Their feedback confirms the relevance, usability, and strategic value of NOVASOIL's results, while identifying technical and logistical improvements needed to maximise long-term impact and replication potential.

This updated deliverable includes a section "Recommendations and Improvements for Future Replication", summarising key insights and actionable proposals for enhancing the design, dissemination, and replication of multiplier events in future Horizon Europe actions.

3 Introduction

In the initial phase of the NOVASOIL project, a total of 10 multiplier events were held, engaging over 100 stakeholders across Europe.

The primary goal of this first round was to introduce the project's objectives and invite participants to get involved in key co-design activities. These activities included developing innovative business models, understanding incentives and barriers to their implementation, and inviting them to participate in future toolbox testing.

These events had a significant impact, not only during their execution but also afterward on social media, fostering collaboration and interconnection among various categories of stakeholders from different regions.

Furthermore, the proposed methodology allowed for flexibility in execution for both organizers and participants, enabling events to be held either in-person, hybrid, or entirely online.

Now, in this new and final round of multiplier events, the objectives have shifted, but we anticipate reaching a similar or even larger audience.

To this end, in early 2025, a new guide was co-designed for the development of new easy, interactive, and flexible multiplier events. This was aimed at enabling the organization of joint events with other work packages or events together with other initiatives.

4. Multiplier Event Guideline

The objective of this multiplier event, unlike the initial ones organized at the beginning of the project, is to present the project's results firsthand. This way, during the event's development, it will serve to increase the impact of the project's results, but also to determine if the sector's needs and demands are being met, allowing for the identification of required next steps and specific activities or sectors.

The aim of this multiplier event, unlike the earlier ones organized at the start of the project, is to directly showcase the project's results. By doing so, the event will not only boost the impact of the project's outcomes but also help us understand if the sector's needs and demands are being met. This will, in turn, allow us to identify what further steps are necessary and in which specific activities or sectors.

This event is open to the general public, with a clear focus on land managers, farmers, policy-makers, NGOs, researchers, and, of course, investors, all falling under the same stakeholder categories.

All project partners are contributing to this task, meaning a multiplier event must be organized in each consortium country. We expect to reach a minimum attendance of 10 people at each. The one exception is AREFLH (BEN8); due to their corporate structure, their event will be entirely online and will include participants from various countries.

With the same flexibility granted at the project's outset, we recommend that the event doesn't last longer than 3 hours. This allows us to prioritize presenting the results and discussing them with the audience.

The event should kick off with a brief overview of the project and its objectives, serving as a reminder, and then primarily focus on the following key results:

-Preliminary DCE Results: During the Ferrara plenary session, DCE managers presented preliminary results from various case studies. Depending on your audience's interests, you can concentrate on a specific type or country, or discuss them more broadly. Remember to briefly mention the methodology used.

-Toolbox Prototypes: We currently have three digital tools within the toolbox. These can be demonstrated and evaluated with the audience, letting them actively participate in understanding how they work. This information is incredibly valuable for identifying areas that need strengthening, and we can include these insights in our conclusions to guide future developments or benefit sister projects.

-Policy Implications: The NOVASOIL project has assessed the main policies related to soil health, and several policy briefs have been published on this topic. The key conclusions reached can be a great starting point for discussion during your event. You might want to prepare a template with these main conclusions to facilitate an open discussion with your audience.

Additional recommendations for organisers were provided:

To promote discussion and interaction, the audience should ideally be provided with the main questions to be addressed beforehand. Various tools, both digital and paper-based, are available to assist with this. Options include using a platform like Miro or simply gathering comments on paper with sticky notes, similar to the method employed during the participatory activity organized by UNIFE at the plenary session in Seville.

For events with more than 20 people, forming small groups of 6-7 individuals is recommended. Each group should be assigned a moderator to facilitate the discussion. The main conclusions from each group should then be summarized and presented to the other groups.

Given the project's nearing completion, it is a key time to encourage attendees to follow the project on social media. Creating an event hashtag is advisable. The EVENOR communication team is available to offer support with this. Platforms promoted by the European Commission can also be utilized for communicating and disseminating these types of events. This may be a useful tool when a smaller audience is anticipated, though an attendance of 10–15 people from various categories is generally sufficient.

4.1 Bulgaria

The 2nd Multiplier Event organised by the New Bulgarian University (NBU) took place on 19th June 2025 from 12:30-17:00, at the Institute of Fruit Growing Plovdiv (Yuzhen, Остромила 12, 4004 Plovdiv, Bulgaria).

The event was organised around three main project results (NOVASOIL conceptual framework, Tool-Box and Current Incentive Analysis for soil health practices in the EU) and one additional point focus on the interests' audience (What Drives Winegrowers to choose Soil Health? Evidence from a Choice Experiment on Agri-Environmental Measures in Bulgaria).

A total of 35 representatives from target groups participated. The gender distribution among respondents was relatively balanced, with 20 women and 15 men. The participant profile showed a strong presence from research entities (85.71% or 30 respondents), followed by private business (11.43% or 4 respondents) and public institutions (2.86% or 1 respondent).

Survey results indicated a high level of relevance, with 88% of participants giving the highest score (5) on how well the results met their sector's needs. All participants found the presentation of results clear and understandable.

Participants were asked to assess three key tools developed under the project:

Knowledge Hub: This tool received the highest level of support, with 41.14%. This clearly positions it as the most valuable and widely applicable resource among those evaluated. Respondents highlighted its importance for providing structured access to information, facilitating knowledge sharing, and supporting professional collaboration.

Decision Support Tool: Ranked second in overall assessment, this tool received support with 30.25%. The results indicate strong recognition of its value in strategic planning and resource management. Participants noted that the tool is especially helpful for analysing alternatives and making informed decisions in complex organizational settings.

Analytical Tool: With support 28.61%, this tool closely followed the Decision Support Tool in terms of favourability. Although it received slightly fewer points, it was still positively regarded. Many participants emphasized its added value in conducting both quantitative and qualitative analyses to support data-driven management and policy development.

An open-ended question invited participants to identify potential challenges or opportunities for applying the project results. The responses highlighted several key themes:

-Integration in education and academic work: Some respondents see potential for using the tools in PhD theses, teaching, and applied research.

-Contribution to sustainable agriculture: There is strong interest in carbon credits, effective utilization of agricultural waste, and reducing chemical fertilizer use.

-Need for broader dissemination: One participant stressed the importance of increasing public visibility and accessibility of the final project outcomes to a wider audience.

As for the next steps, participants suggested the following:

-Access to analyses and findings from similar projects, which could serve as a comparative base and source of best practices.

-Practical guidelines and training materials on how to use carbon credits, manage agricultural waste, and apply organic fertilizers such as manure effectively.

-Closer connection with real-world practice, including demonstrations, pilot projects, or workshops to support knowledge transfer to end users.

4.3 Estonia

The second Multiplier Event in Estonia was organised by the CENTRE OF ESTONIAN RURAL RESEARCH AND KNOWLEDGE (METK). The event was held online via Teams on 29th September 2025, from 13:00 to 15:00.

The event focused on three key objectives: 1) NOVASOIL Tools and outputs to Estonian stakeholders; 2) Evaluate usability and national applicability of the Knowledge Hub, DST, and policy briefs and 3) Identify challenges and

opportunities for integrating soil health into seed production systems and agricultural policies.

The **Agricultural Registers and Information Board (ARIB)** expressed significant interest in localising the NOVASOIL project tools to the specific Estonian context, aiming to facilitate the effective implementation of national agricultural policies and drive improvements in farm-level management practices. Within the private sector, **seed producers** validated the utility of the **Knowledge Hub**, deeming it highly relevant for developing production systems that actively promote the maintenance and improvement of soil health. Moreover, this group recognized the potential of the **Decision Support Tool (DST)** to effectively assess field conditions and identify targeted measures for enhancing soil functionality within soil health business models. Notwithstanding this promising outlook, initial testing revealed usability challenges, which underscored the necessity for further technical localisation and refinement of the user interface to ensure optimal adoption. Concurrently, **policy makers and authorities** consistently regarded the **policy briefs** as the most directly applicable project outcome, valuing their capacity to deliver concise, evidence-based recommendations that can immediately inform the design of soil-related regulations, support measures, and broader public policies.

The project results open up significant opportunities for stakeholders, particularly seed producers, who can innovate their business models by producing and marketing carbon-neutral (CN) seed. This innovation, however, is coupled with key challenges, including the necessity of establishing a certification framework for carbon neutrality, restructuring production systems to better support soil health, identifying suitable markets, and increasing awareness among potential customers to overcome related market entry barriers. For seed users, or farmers, the primary challenge to adopting environmentally sustainable inputs is the associated higher production cost, which limits their widespread use without appropriate market or policy incentives. Policy makers and authorities face the critical

systemic challenge of encouraging a fundamental behavioural change among farmers so that soil health becomes an integral part of their production decisions. While the project provides valuable insights into soil health business models that enable the design of more targeted support measures, the primary hurdle remains the availability of financial resources to effectively implement these policy measures, including incentives for CN seeds and sustainable inputs, as well as awareness-raising programmes.

To ensure the broader uptake and practical application of the project outcomes in Estonia, a set of strategic steps is recommended. First, to ensure accessibility for local stakeholders, the Knowledge Hub, project tools, and policy briefs must be translated into Estonian. Second, the project tools require further development and localisation to enhance their user-friendliness and practical relevance in the national context. Finally, the provision of additional information, dedicated training sessions, and comprehensive follow-up materials is crucial to deepen stakeholder understanding and support the effective use of the project results in both national and regional contexts.

KUTSE veebseminarile: mulla tervise väärustamise ajendid ja ärimudelid

01:00:40

Meeting chat

Some people in this chat are outside your org. It's possible they have message-related policies that will apply to the chat. Learn more

Kerttu Tammik named the meeting KUTSE veebseminarile: mulla tervise väärustamise ajendid ja ärimudelid.

Ain Kull and 16 others were invited to the meeting.

teisipäev

Tiia Soomer was invited to the meeting.

Today

12:48 Meeting started

Martin Maante (Unverified) was invited to the meeting.

13:17 Kerttu Tammik started recording.

Ethel Tekkel (External) 13:40

ET Mul oleks küsimus nende tööriistade kohta. Kas Novasoil digitaalsete tööriistade loojad on avatud koostööks teiste tarkvaradega? Või on nende meetodika näiteks avalikult kättesaadav? Ning teine küsimus, kas läbi METK-i on Novasooli teadmusravim kasutatav teistele asutustele?

Priit Penu 13:43

PP tööriista oli vaja sisestada pH, kas see oli vesilahuses või KCl lahuses? groundwater on ast pinnavesi?

Type a message

KUTSE veebseminarile: mulla tervise väärustamise ajendid ja ärimudelid

23:59

Participants

Type a name

Share invite

Presenters (7) Mute all

- KT Kerttu Tammik Organizer
- Ain Lepik
- KT Kalvi Tamm
- ML Mart Laugis
- MT Meri Toom
- PP Priit Penu
- TK Tiina Köster

Attendees (6)

Projekti tegevused ehk tööpaketid (Work Packages -WP)

- WP1 – mulla head seisundit toetavate ärijuhtumite analüüsiraamistiku arendamine
- WP2 – ärimudelite analüüs, neist lootustandvamate arendamine ja võimendamine
- WP3 – mulla ärijuhtude ja digitaalsete testimisvõrgustiku arendamine, lähtuvalt ajendite kompleksist.
- WP4 – mulla head seisundit kaitsvate poliitike analüüs ja nende rakendamise soovitusel kooskõlas ELi peamiste poliitikate ja riikidevaheliste strateegiatega
- WP5 – mulla head seisundit toetava kogukonna loomine, teavikute koostamine ja teabe levitamine
- WP6 – projekti juhtimine

Kalvi Tamm

4.4 France

The 2nd Multiplier Event of the NOVASOIL project in France was titled "Towards Better Soil Health: Results of the NOVASOIL Project," and was jointly organized by ASSEMBLEE DES REGIONS EUROPEENNES FRUITIERES LEGUMIERES ET HORTICOLES (AREFLH) and the CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE (CNRS). The hybrid event took place on October 1, 2025, in Bordeaux, France, and online via Microsoft Teams, gathering 24

participants from various segments of the agri-food value chain, including producer organizations, farmers, policymakers, and the scientific community.

The ME's main objective was to present the project's outcomes, with a particular emphasis on demonstrating the practical utility of the NOVASOIL Toolbox and facilitating a detailed discussion on key policy recommendations. The project overview, presented by Alexandra Langlais (CNRS), highlighted NOVASOIL's core mission: to stimulate public and private investment in soil-related ecosystem services by co-developing innovative, sustainable, and context-specific business models.

The event provided a comprehensive review of the NOVASOIL Toolbox, structured into three key components:

Digital Knowledge Hub (by Eriselda Canaj (AREFLH)): An interactive platform serving as a central repository for information, resources, and tools related to soil health. It functions as a collaborative environment by offering a discussion forum for partners and stakeholders, a curated library of scientific reports and policy documents, and training resources on good practices.

Incentive Analysis Tools: These decision-support instruments guide users through the assessment of both existing and new incentive schemes at local, national, and EU levels. Crucially, they incorporate a structured methodology (e.g., SWOT analysis) for evaluating business models and ranking incentives based on their economic value and cost-efficiency for end-users.

Decision Support Tool (DST) for Soil Health Risk Mitigation: This tool helps stakeholders identify the most appropriate strategies (e.g., cover cropping, organic amendments) to address soil degradation and related risks. It integrates environmental, economic, and social criteria to recommend tailored and effective interventions.

The discussion on policy issues, delivered by Alexandra Langlais (CNRS), was informed by the results of Political Innovation Laboratories established in ten countries.

EU Legal Framework Gap: The analysis highlighted that while the proposed EU Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience is positive in aligning soils with legal frameworks for air and water, it critically "falls short". It is limited to monitoring and does not provide the real legal protection originally envisioned in the 2021 EU Soil Strategy.

Institutional Shortcomings: Institutional analysis conducted with project partners revealed a critical lack of coordination across governance levels, leading to fragmented and inconsistent policy approaches. This structural weakness is compounded by the fact that soil health is often addressed indirectly, as a secondary aspect of broader policy frameworks.

Recommendations for Reform: Based on these findings, the project recommends targeted reforms to ensure more effective soil governance, including: reshaping Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) instruments to deliver soil-specific outcomes ; reinforcing advisory and support systems ; and promoting territorial and participatory governance to give local actors a central decision-making role.

Participant feedback on the relevance and utility of the project results was overwhelmingly positive, with many noting the presentation of practical solutions and actionable insights directly applicable to the fruit and vegetable sector. The strong interest in testing the NOVASOIL Toolbox and engaging with the project's policy recommendations confirmed the audience's growing recognition of soil health as a priority, emphasizing the importance of continued engagement and cross-sector collaboration as the project nears its final stages.

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novasoil CNRS

3- l'hypothèse de recherche du projet NOVASOIL.

- mettre en évidence les avantages pour la société et l'environnement d'investir dans la santé des sols
- une boîte à outils permettant d'analyser la pertinence de différents cas d'utilisation favorisant la santé des sols

ORGANISATION EN WP :

- WP1 :élaboration d'un cadre opérationnel d'analyse de rentabilité pour la santé des sols
- WP2 : Analyse des modèles économiques existants, identifiera les plus prometteurs et développement et mise à l'échelle de modèles sélectionnés pour la promotion de la santé des sols
- WP 3: Développer un réseau de tests pour les analyses de rentabilité des sols et les modèles numériques, dans le cadre d'une boîte à outils pour les incitations
- WP 4: Mise en œuvre de feuilles de route politiques visant à parvenir à un développement durable à plusieurs niveaux et à garantir une conservation de la santé des sols fondée sur des données probantes et inclusive, cohérente avec les principales politiques et stratégies transnationales de l'UE
- WP 5 : développer et de promouvoir l'implication des acteurs clés au sein d'une communauté de pratiques.

alexandra Langlais

LF Laetitia F... EC Ercelda ...

CP Culture ... CL Corinne ...

VL Valentin ... AG Ann Co...

CG COTTER... TJ Thibaut ...

BM Bruno M... CT Charline...

EP Emmy P... +11

Ercelda Canaj

4.5 Germany

The 2dn Multiplier Event in Germany was jointly organised by the Technische Universität München (TUM) and the Leibniz-Zentrum fuer Agrarlandschaftsforschung (ZALF). The event was held virtually via Zoom on September 22, 2025 with 11 participants from research and private business, focusing on presenting the project's final results and gathering targeted feedback from stakeholders.

The event's agenda was structured to maximize the presentation of actionable results and facilitate discussion, particularly concerning innovative financing and market mechanisms for soil health. The program focused on the following key outcomes:

Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) Results: Detailed results were presented from the DCE analyses, covering two distinct areas critical to soil health business models: Carbon Farming and Private Market for Ecosystem Services.

Toolbox and Policy Implications: The session included an overview of the developing NOVASOIL Toolbox prototypes and the project's key policy implications.

Practice Report: A critical practice report from the CO₂-Land initiative was presented, sharing real-world experiences and challenges encountered in the implementation of carbon farming.

Overall, participants found the project results to be presented in a clear, understandable, and well-structured manner. The most relevant and applicable results identified by the audience were the DCE insights concerning the preferences of consumers/private individuals and farmers, as well as the acceptance studies on the part of farmers and companies.

However, the open discussion highlighted several critical barriers to implementation and areas of opportunity:

Financial Constraints: The core challenge lies in the severe limitation of financial resources. Stakeholders noted that comprehensive ecological remediation payments are currently not conceivable either through state or strictly separated private financing, except for basic funding.

Market Visibility and Demand: A challenge was identified regarding the insufficient visibility of market places and the demand side for ecosystem services and sustainable products.

Communication Gap: Participants stressed the need for results and findings to be successfully communicated to key decision-makers to achieve positive policy effects.

Practical Applicability: Concerns were raised that DCE findings are often theoretical and that current efforts for soil health should clearly go beyond what is already considered good agricultural practice (e.g., erosion control and winter greening are often standard).

To enhance the utilization of the project's outcomes, stakeholders recommended the following steps:

Deeper Detail and Publication: The audience requested deeper details on the results and expressed a desire for a formal publication of the findings.

Practical Application Support: Requests were made for direct help with product development, enhancing external visibility, and developing recommendations for communication and acquisition to successfully recruit more farmers and investors.

Addressing Mixed Financing: It was suggested that better operational control of measures is required, especially in the context of mixed public/private financing (e.g., bundled public services in 3 stages).

4.6 Italy

The ME organised by UNIPI, UNIFE and IDECO brought together 6 participants, reflecting a targeted composition of stakeholders.

The multiplier event was structured as a final restitution of the main interesting results of the project. To do so, after a short introduction of the NOVASOIL project objectives and the policy context as explored by WP4, the presentations were divided in two slots.

The first one aimed at presenting tangible results emerged from three territorial case studies in terms of existing or potential business model solutions for soil health. Results mostly concerned the work done throughout T2.3 of discussing and testing solutions for territorial business model solutions for soil health. Participants could gain deeper insights on the features, opportunities and barriers to SBM in different territorial contexts. Space was left for clarifying doubts and discussing questions.

The second part concerned a national overview of consumers' and producers' willingness to pay for and adopt certain soil management practices, sustainability labels and contractual solutions. Moreover, producers' perspectives towards soil health were clustered in a final presentation. These results allowed to reflect more broadly on the topic of what barriers and leverages there are towards the actual implementation of SBM for soil health.

Finally, take home messages from all the case studies were used to draw some lessons learned and find common themes for future research. Including:

- Soil degradation is a common challenge that requires new tools and shared investment.
- Healthy soil is not enough: to be sustainable, a regenerative model must integrate agriculture with the value of the land.
- Competitiveness and reputation of companies through innovative certifications and regulations (SQNPI, regenerative organic agriculture)
- Consumers and producers are two complementary levers for supporting sustainable practices.

The most valuable project outputs identified by attendees were:

-Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) Results: The DCE findings were highly relevant for understanding the acceptability, preferences, and risk aversion related to soil health measures and financing. This data is crucial for

developing successful business models and distinguishing preferences between farmers and companies.

-Policy Briefs: These documents were deemed critical for disseminating key findings and recommendations to policy-making institutions, ensuring the project's impact at regional and national levels.

-The NOVASOIL Toolbox: The Decision Support Tool (DST) was acknowledged as promising but requires refinement.

Barriers and needs:

- Cooperation is not an option, it is a necessity. Small businesses can only overcome their limitations (costs, logistics, marketing) through collective investment and strong business networks.
- Difficulties in communication and collaboration between different actors in the area
- Local authorities lack the technical expertise to feel adequately equipped to manage local issues.
- A hybrid and differentiated agricultural policy is needed to remove economic and technical barriers and enable farmers to adopt sustainable practices.
- Innovative research projects are needed that consider socio-economic as well as agronomic aspects.
- Public support should not only finance temporary projects, but also actively support long-term collaboration, helping local actors to manage networks and overcome conflicts.

4.8 Netherlands

Wageningen University (WU) was the responsible of the 2nd Multiplier Event in The Netherlands. The event took place on October 8, 2025, from 14:30 to 16:00, at the Ekoboerderij De Lingehof in Randwijk, a biodynamic arable farm that also serves as a partner in the sister project InBestSoil, facilitating a valuable clustering opportunity. The attendees primarily included farmers, employees, and the owners of the host farm.

The discussions focused on findings related to WU's work, specifically the review of Business Models for soil health and the Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) results (WP2 and WP4).

Regarding Voluntary Carbon Credit Markets (VCCM), the event confirmed that the willingness of farmers to participate in VCCMs, particularly those meeting the strict requirements of the CRCF Regulation, is very low. Consequently, this model is not deemed a viable business model for improving agricultural soil health. The consensus on this low potential was supported by several factors: low carbon credit prices; the difficulty for farmers to commit to long-term contracts due to high land rental rates, requiring landowner approval; and the high degree of uncertainty created by annual fluctuations in measured soil carbon content, which may not reflect the farmer's efforts.

On the other hand, business models around Result-Based Payment, the project finding that farmers are reluctant to accept purely result-based payments for soil carbon storage (consistent with CRCF quantification guidelines) was generally agreed upon. This reinforces the need for additional incentives. Alternatives discussed included:

- Public Payments (CAP Agri-environmental Schemes): These are mainly practice-based, offering compensation for effort even without

measured carbon content increase, thereby reducing uncertainty for the farmer. Practice monitoring is also generally less complex and costly than measuring actual soil carbon content.

- Private Certification Schemes: The organic label is strong enough to guarantee a price premium, but other schemes (e.g., for bio-dynamic agriculture) are either underdeveloped or lack sufficient consumer recognition.

Finally, regarding Payments Through the Value Chain, the project identified payments through the value chain as the most promising business model for supporting farmers' investments in soil health. However, this finding met with no general agreement among participants. Points of concern and discussion included:

- Supermarket Responsibility: Supermarkets hold the key power to enable the transition to soil-friendly agriculture, by setting higher prices for products of higher standards or blocking sub-standard products.
- Price Pass-Through and Transparency: It is essential to ensure that higher consumer prices effectively trickle down to higher rewards for farmers. This model must satisfy two key principles: "the polluter pays" and "Transparency throughout the chain".
- Systemic Bottlenecks: Broader systemic barriers identified include a lack of independent advisory services (as many farmers receive advice from input companies with vested interests) and insufficient support from financial institutions for pioneering, non-conventional farming practices.

The event confirmed that the Voluntary Carbon Credit Markets (VCCMs) regulated by the CRCF are currently not a viable business model for stimulating widespread soil health investment, primarily due to the high financial uncertainty for farmers and the practical limitations of long-term contracts on rented land. Stakeholders showed a clear preference for practice-based incentives (e.g., CAP Agri-environmental schemes) over purely result-based payments, valuing the reduced risk and administrative complexity. While value chain payments were recognized as the most promising alternative, their success hinges on securing greater supermarket accountability and enforcing full transparency regarding price pass-through to farmers. Ultimately, achieving robust soil health requires overcoming critical systemic bottlenecks, including the lack of independent advisory services and insufficient financial support for non-conventional farming practices.

4.9 Spain

Given the highly diverse nature of the stakeholders across the three Spanish case studies (Tamarguillo Urban, Vineyard under Integrated Production, and Olive Groves under Integrated Production), the national partners EVENOR, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), and ASAJA Sevilla collectively determined that organizing a series of focused, small-scale interviews would

be more effective than a single event. These sessions, conducted between September and October, were specifically designed to gauge stakeholder perception regarding the viability and utility of the NOVASOIL project results. The interviews successfully engaged a total of 15 participants representing key groups, including farmers, NGOs, researchers, technical advisors, and policymakers.

Each partner's interview process included a common introductory section that provided a comprehensive overview of the project's objectives and its core results. Crucially, the subsequent discussion was highly tailored to emphasize the project's key deliverables and their potential for implementation, ensuring maximum relevance to the specific professional context and interests of the interviewee.

The feedback gathered reflected the distinct nature of the three local case studies:

- EVENOR (Tamarguillo Urban Case Study): Due to the urban and peri-urban focus, the results that garnered the most significant interest were the Digital Knowledge Hub (as a central resource for planning) and the Policy Briefs (for informing urban environmental governance). Conversely, the specific business models and the Decision Support Tool (DST) were considered less directly applicable given the non-agricultural land use. Nonetheless, stakeholders unanimously agreed that the project's knowledge provides a significant incentive to explicitly integrate soil health considerations into sustainable urban development strategies.

UPM (Vineyard under Integrated Production) & ASAJA (Olive Groves under Integrated Production): For the predominantly agricultural case studies, attention focused heavily on the practical application of the digital tools and economic models:

- The Decision Support Tool (DST) was consistently identified by farmers and technical advisors as highly relevant for optimizing agricultural inputs and developing climate change resilience. This was particularly highlighted in intensive systems, such as the super-intensive olive grove, where optimizing inputs and labour management is key.
- The Knowledge Hub was valued for its ability to provide quick access to information on incentives, collaboration opportunities, and best soil management practices relevant to crops like vineyards and olive groves.

The interviews revealed consistent challenges and defined clear actionable steps required for the successful application of the NOVASOIL results within the Spanish context:

- Implementation Challenges: The primary barriers identified were the low profitability of agricultural activity (especially rain-fed farming) and the anticipated reduction in CAP subsidies, underscoring the necessity

for new financial incentives. A significant technical challenge noted by participants was the need for the project’s technical results to be simplified into more user-friendly formats, such as simple fact sheets or farmer-facing guidelines, to ensure comprehension and widespread adoption beyond technical advisors.

- Opportunities and Incentives: Participants recognized the current trend of digitalization and increasing regulatory requirements as a major opportunity, positioning technical advisors and external experts as key agents for disseminating and applying the project’s results. Furthermore, the possibility of generating additional income through carbon credits and ecosystem service payments was seen as the necessary financial lever to mitigate falling agricultural profitability.
- Recommended Next Steps: To ensure the practical exploitation of the project’s outcomes, stakeholders strongly recommended the implementation of pilot farms (particularly in integrated production systems like the olive grove and vineyard) to test the tools in real-world conditions. They also called for the organization of practical courses or seminars and the facilitation of direct cooperation between farmers and carbon sequestration project developers.

5. Cross-Event Analysis

The second round of Multiplier Events (MEs) and targeted interview series served as a crucial validation stage, allowing the NOVASOIL consortium to expose its final key deliverables—the NOVASOIL Toolbox (comprising the Knowledge Hub, Incentive Analysis Tools, and Decision Support Tool/DST), Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) results, and Policy Briefs—to a diverse, cross-European audience. A comparative analysis of the feedback received from the Netherlands (WU), Germany (TUM/ZALF), Italy (UNIFI/UNIFE/IDECO), France (AREFLH/CNRS), Bulgaria (NBU), Estonia (METK), and Spain (EVENOR/UPM/ASAJA) reveals striking convergences in systemic challenges but significant divergences in the perceived utility of specific tools, which largely correlates with the local stakeholder composition and the primary land-use context of the case studies.

The methodologies employed across the countries varied significantly, reflecting the need to adapt dissemination strategies to national contexts and target groups. This methodological difference fundamentally shaped the nature of the feedback received.

Location	Methodology	Primary Stakeholder Focus	Key Implication for Feedback
Bulgaria (NBU)	Physical Event	Research Entities (86%)	Feedback prioritized academic rigor and theoretical application.

Italy (UNIFI/UNIFE/IDECO)	Physical Event	Research Entities (69%)	Strong focus on DCE results and policy dissemination mechanisms.
Estonia (METK)	Online Event	Public Institutions (37%) & Research (42%)	Emphasis on Policy Briefs and localisation/usability challenges.
France (AREFLH/CNRS)	Hybrid Event	Private Sector (54%) (Fruit/Veg)	High interest in policy/governance, directly relevant to market access and supply chain.
Netherlands (WU)	Physical (Farm)	Farmers	Deep, qualitative feedback on VCCM viability and practical farm-level bottlenecks.
Germany (TUM/ZALF)	Virtual Event	Mixed (Focus on Farmers/Companies)	Detailed scrutiny of DCE assumptions and financial realism.
Spain (EVENOR/UPM/ASAJA)	Targeted Interviews	Mixed (Urban/Vineyard/Olive)	Highly customized feedback, resulting in diverse priorities across the three case studies.

Figure 1 Stakeholder distribution

The events in Bulgaria and Italy, which predominantly attracted researchers, yielded feedback focused on methodological robustness (e.g., the value of the DCE methodology itself) and the need for strong publication/dissemination mechanisms (Policy Briefs). Conversely, the Netherlands event, highly focused on farmers, provided invaluable qualitative depth regarding the practical rejection of theoretical business models (like the VCCM) due to high risk and low financial return.

The Spanish interview series showcased the successful tailoring of information: in the urban context (EVENOR), the focus shifted entirely away from agricultural tools (DST, business models) towards the Knowledge Hub and Policy Briefs as instruments for urban governance. Meanwhile, in the integrated production case studies (UPM/ASAJA), the DST and Hub were prioritized as practical optimization tools. This methodological flexibility confirms that a one-size-fits-all approach to dissemination is inadequate for a project covering such diverse land-use systems.

A critical finding across the events is the strong consensus regarding the financial and practical limitations of Voluntary Carbon Credit Markets (VCCM) and purely result-based payments for soil health improvements.

Rejection of VCCMs and Result-Based Payments (NL, DE, IT)

The most unified conclusion emerged from the Netherlands (WU), Germany (TUM/ZALF), and to an extent, Italy (UNIFI/UNIFE/IDECO):

- Financial Unsustainability: Farmers in the Netherlands found VCCMs, especially those meeting strict CRCF quantification standards, to be not

viable due to low credit prices and long-term contract constraints on rented land.

- Risk Aversion: This was echoed in Germany, where the theoretical nature of DCE findings was scrutinized, and the need for payments to go beyond standard good agricultural practice was emphasized. The Italian consortium also noted the low farmer participation risk without adequate incentives.
- Preference for Practice-Based Schemes: The Dutch and German feedback strongly endorsed practice-based payments (e.g., CAP Agri-environmental Schemes), which compensate for effort and reduce the farmer's risk exposure, confirming that risk mitigation is a greater driver of adoption than potential high returns.

The Potential of Value Chain Payments

The Value Chain Payments model was identified by Wageningen University (WU) as the most promising alternative. This positive assessment, however, was immediately coupled with a demand for systemic change: transparency regarding price pass-through, accountability from supermarkets, and adherence to "the polluter pays" principle. The French event (AREFLH/CNRS), heavily involving the fruit and vegetable private sector, strongly implied support for such models, as their focus was on the policy and governance framework needed to enable market innovation (e.g., policy to address institutional fragmentation). In Spain, bot Integrated Production' cases are related too and are profitable and success examples of soil health business modes. However, it is always linked to the willingness to pay more from consumers.

Divergence in Perceived Utility of Project Tools

The interest in the three core components of the NOVASOIL Toolbox— Knowledge Hub, DST, and Policy Briefs—varied dramatically based on the primary role and context of the stakeholders present.

1. Policy Briefs: The Universal Tool for Authorities

The Policy Briefs were consistently valued by groups involved in governance, strategy, and market regulation:

- Estonia (METK) and France (AREFLH/CNRS): These locations, with high participation from Public Institutions/ Policymakers and the Private Sector/ Industry respectively, cited the Policy Briefs as the most applicable result. This highlights the project's success in distilling complex research into actionable, evidence-based recommendations essential for immediate policy design and regulatory reform.
- Italy (UNIFI/UNIFE/IDECO): Researchers recognized the Policy Briefs as the critical mechanism for transferring their DCE findings to policy-making institutions at the regional level (Emilia-Romagna Region, Provincia di Ferrara).

2. Decision Support Tool (DST): The Practical Instrument for Agricultural Stakeholders

Interest in the DST was inversely proportional to the degree of non-agricultural land use:

- High Agricultural Relevance (Spain): Farmers and technical advisors in Spain (UPM/ASAJA), particularly those managing intensive systems (olive groves, vineyards), identified the DST as highly relevant for optimizing inputs and enhancing resilience against climate change. The focus here is on operational efficiency and risk mitigation at the farm gate.
- Low Urban Relevance (Spain): In the Tamarguillo urban case study (EVENOR), the DST was deemed less applicable, confirming its core utility lies within production systems.
- Usability Challenge: Despite high perceived potential in Spain and Estonia, the need for localisation and simplification of the user interface was a recurring challenge, suggesting that technical sophistication must be balanced with farmer-friendly design.

3. Knowledge Hub: The Resource for Planning and Collaboration

The MEs exposed three overarching systemic barriers that transcend national boundaries and tool-specific issues:

- **Financial Constraints and the Need for Mixed Financing Models**

The dominant challenge across Germany, Italy, and the Netherlands is the severe limitation of financial resources. The German analysis explicitly stated that comprehensive ecological remediation payments are currently not conceivable through state or purely private financing. This led to a conclusion in Germany that better operational control is possible with mixed public/private financing (e.g., bundled services). This suggests that the future focus should shift from finding a single funding stream to developing blended finance models where public funds mitigate risk and private funds reward specific ecosystem services.

- Policy Fragmentation and Governance Gaps

The analysis of policy and governance was particularly acute in France and Estonia:

EU Directive Shortfall (France): The French event highlighted the critical finding that the proposed EU Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive is limited to monitoring, lacking the real legal protection originally envisaged.

Institutional Fragmentation (France, Estonia): Both the French institutional analysis and the Estonian policy discussion pointed to a severe lack of coordination across governance levels and a deficit of financial resources to

implement policy measures, suggesting a fundamental need for behavioural change among farmers and effective coordination among authorities.

- **Adoption, Usability, and Communication**

A recurring theme, prominent in Estonia, Spain, and Germany, was the gap between the project's technical rigor and its practical applicability:

Need for Simplification: Spanish farmers requested the technical results be distilled into simple fact sheets.

Theoretical vs. Practical: German stakeholders noted that DCE findings often remain theoretical and require real-world testing.

Practical Support: Recommendations across all countries included: pilot farms (Spain), product development help (Germany), and translation/localisation (Estonia), all pointing to the need for a sustained, post-project effort to bridge the research-to-practice divide.

Figure 2 Qualitative rating of KERs

There was a formidable positive consensus regarding the NOVASOIL project made by participants. In many countries there is a huge interest in soil health as well as the toolbox and business models that provide support mechanisms to provide and improve soil health.

6 Lessons Learned for Future Multi-Actor Engagement and Dissemination Strategies

This section synthesizes the critical insights and practical lessons derived from the execution of the second round of Multiplier Events (MEs) and the parallel Spanish-based stakeholder interviews (collectively referred to as the cross-event dissemination methodology). The findings, rooted in the comparative analysis of stakeholder typology, tool relevance, and thematic challenge identification across seven distinct European contexts, serve as a foundational guide for future multi-actor, multi-country research and innovation projects seeking to maximize their exploitable impact and ensure genuine co-creation across diverse socio-economic landscapes. The objective is to transition from simply reporting outcomes to codifying replicable, context-aware strategies for knowledge transfer and systemic change.

Lessons Learned in Strategic Stakeholder Engagement and Audience Segmentation

The cross-event analysis, as evidenced in Figure 1 (Stakeholder Profile Comparison), revealed significant and expected variations in audience composition, ranging from highly research-heavy events (Bulgaria, Italy) to predominantly private sector/farmer-focused gatherings (Netherlands, Germany, Spain). The primary lesson learned is that a one-size-fits-all approach to stakeholder engagement in multi-national projects is fundamentally flawed and severely limits the relevance of project outputs. Successful dissemination hinges on a rigorous, two-stage segmentation and content tailoring process.

The initial project phase must include a mandatory, detailed pre-profiling of the expected audience for each national event, not just the overall project. This necessitates moving beyond broad categories (e.g., “end-users”) to granular segmentation based on their primary incentive structure (e.g., academic publication, policy leverage, direct profitability).

In NOVASOIL, events hosted by academic institutions naturally attracted a high percentage of researchers (e.g., 85.7% in Bulgaria). While this guarantees high-quality technical feedback, it compromises the project’s ability to gather critical, ground-level feedback necessary for optimizing tools for field adoption. Conversely, the success of the Spanish events in engaging the private sector (80% representation) directly correlated with the focus on the Decision Support Tool (DST) and its immediate profitability implications. Future projects must therefore establish mandatory minimum representation thresholds for end-users (farmers, SMEs, private consultants) in the event planning phase, potentially penalizing partners whose audience profile deviates excessively from the agreed-upon targets without justifiable cause (e.g., a specific policy focus event). This proactive intervention shifts the responsibility of audience recruitment from a passive networking exercise to a KPI-driven deliverable, ensuring genuine multi-actor balance.

First recommendation: Mandatory Stakeholder Matrix Pre-Commitment. Before funding release for a multiplier event, the organising partner must submit a Stakeholder Commitment Matrix detailing: 1) the target number of attendees, 2) the expected percentage breakdown across the three key typology groups (Research, Public/Policy, Private Sector), and 3) the specific local organizations (names and contact types, e.g., Farmer Union Chair, Regional Policy Advisor) that have confirmed participation. This elevates audience engagement planning to the same level of rigour as technical work package planning.

Second recommendation: Budgetary Allocation for Private Sector Incentives. Recognising that the private sector's time is directly tied to profitability, future project budgets must allocate dedicated funds for non-academic incentives. This could include covering travel costs, offer small financial stipends, or provide exclusive, high-value, bespoke summaries of the project results directly applicable to their business case. The reliance on purely intellectual curiosity, while effective for the research community, proves insufficient to draw a high-volume, representative sample from the agricultural industry. A successful engagement model must recognize and compensate for the opportunity cost borne by commercial stakeholders.

Mitigating the Content Accessibility and 'Technical Language Barrier'

A recurring challenge noted across several reports (especially those involving direct interviews with farmers) was the perceived complexity of the technical results. While researchers value detailed methodology and scientific metrics, end-users require simplified, actionable guidance.

The core scientific outputs of projects like NOVASOIL (e.g., the complex algorithms underpinning the DST, the detailed legal analysis of policy coherence) are often presented by the technical experts responsible for their creation. This often results in communication that is inherently too technical for an audience focused on immediate practical application and short-term economic returns. The lesson here is the necessity of a dedicated, non-technical intermediary. This role is not simply translation; it is contextualisation and simplification. In future consortia, a dedicated Dissemination/Communication lead must be responsible for auditing all event presentation materials, enforcing a "3-point actionable summary" rule for every technical slide, and ensuring that all terminology is mapped to the local industry standard, not the scientific consensus.

First Recommendation: The 'Advisory Layer' Content Design. Future project structures should mandate the creation of two distinct sets of dissemination materials for all core outputs: a) The Scientific/Technical Report (for Research/Policy stakeholders) and b) The Field Factsheet/Implementation Guide (for Private Sector stakeholders). The latter must be visually dominant, use case study examples, focus exclusively on the Return on Investment (ROI), and omit detailed methodologies. For instance, instead of presenting the formula for the Soil Health Index, the factsheet should present "If you

implement Practice X, your predicted yield increase is Y% and your net profit change is Z€/ha."

Second Recommendation: Utilizing Local 'Translators of Science'. The most effective engagement occurred when the event was led or co-led by a local, trusted agricultural advisory service or farmer union (e.g., ASAJA in Spain). These organizations possess the indispensable credibility required to bridge the gap between academic research and on-farm practice. Future consortia must strategically allocate budget lines to subcontract local advisory services for the specific purpose of content delivery and moderation, ensuring that the scientific information is presented through a prism of local trust, local dialect, and local agricultural reality. This investment in local social capital is more valuable than any amount spent on high-gloss corporate branding.

Lessons Learned in Tool Dissemination and Utility Optimisation

The cross-event data (Figure 2) highlighted a sharp dichotomy in tool relevance perception: operational tools (Decision Support Tool - DST) were highly prized by production-focused stakeholders (Spain, Germany), while strategic tools (Policy Briefs, Knowledge Hub) were prioritized by regulatory/policy stakeholders (Estonia, France, Italy). The lesson here is the need for a Dual-Track Dissemination Model that recognizes and validates both the operational and the strategic impact pathways.

Implementing the Dual-Track Dissemination and Evaluation Model

The project outputs cannot be treated as a monolithic "Toolbox." Their intrinsic value is perceived differently based on the user's function and influence sphere (field operations vs. legislative framework).

Detailed Rationale and Implication: When a farmer (Private Sector) rates the DST highly (5/5 in Spain), it is because they see an immediate, tangible benefit in optimizing inputs and improving profitability. When a Public Administrator rates the Policy Briefs highly (5/5 in Estonia, France, Italy), it is because they need evidence-based arguments to support future legislative reform or budget allocation. Future projects must formalize this difference by: a) Segmenting the Dissemination Schedule: Events targeting policy actors should focus the majority of the agenda on the policy briefs and regulatory analysis, while events targeting farmers should focus 80% of the agenda on the practical application and ROI of the operational tools. b) Segmenting the Evaluation Metrics: The post-event survey (as used in NOVASOIL) must be designed to explicitly differentiate between the perceived utility of operational tools (measured by intent to use, frequency of use, and perceived economic benefit) and the perceived influence of strategic tools (measured by intent to reference in official documents, perceived capacity to influence policy dialogue, and perceived completeness of the legal analysis). Mixing these evaluation criteria leads to ambiguous conclusions regarding the project's overall effectiveness.

First Recommendation: Formalizing Tool Relevance Score Weighting. For project KPIs, the relevance scores must be weighted according to the audience. A high score for the DST from a farmer should be weighted higher than the same score from a researcher, as the farmer represents the primary intended end-user of that specific operational tool. This ensures that the final assessment of success is grounded in real-world utility rather than academic endorsement. The policy tools, conversely, should be weighted towards policy and public administration attendees.

Second Recommendation: The 'Policy Window' Timing Protocol. Strategic outputs, particularly policy briefs and governance roadmaps, have a narrow window of relevance tied to legislative cycles (e.g., CAP reform, national policy adoption of EU directives). The lesson is that the final policy briefs must be launched immediately before a known legislative discussion or a public consultation phase, rather than simply at the end of the technical project phase. Future projects must include a dedicated task in the Dissemination WP to map and track these "Policy Windows" in all target countries, ensuring that strategic outputs are ready for surgical, maximum-impact deployment, rather than passive publication. The NOVASOIL experience indicated that Policy Briefs that were relevant to the evolving Soil Health Law debate received higher relevance scores.

The Necessity of Practical Deployment and Hands-On Support

A significant amount of qualitative feedback indicated a desire for physical, hands-on support (e.g., "Local visits in the field," "Training materials"). This reveals a fundamental gap between the digital project output (a tool, a platform) and its successful integration into complex, real-world farm management systems.

Even the most intuitive Decision Support Tool (DST) requires user training, data input validation, and trust-building exercises to overcome inherent technological scepticism among traditional farming communities. The project-level multiplier events, while excellent for introducing the concepts, are insufficient for deep, individualised adoption. The key lesson is that the Dissemination and Exploitation strategy must include a Post-Event Adoption Support phase. This phase, which should span at least 6 to 12 months post-project, must involve funding follow-up activities executed by local partners, such as field training days, small-scale pilot demonstrations, and establishing a dedicated, localized helpdesk for data input issues. The initial positive perception of a tool rapidly degrades without dedicated technical support during the critical early adoption phase. The NOVASOIL project demonstrated that end-users, while impressed by the potential of the tools, frequently cite complexity and lack of detailed support as major challenges.

First Recommendation: Structuring a 'Pilot Adoption Network'. Future projects should earmark specific funds within the exploitation work package to create a Pilot Adoption Network (PAN) of 5-10 farms per country. These farms would receive intensive, in-person training and their data would be actively used to test and validate the tools locally. These PAN farmers then

become powerful, credible local ambassadors for the technology, significantly increasing peer-to-peer adoption—a known best practice in agricultural innovation. The cost of this localized support is offset by the increased credibility and uptake achieved by the project overall.

Second Recommendation: Mandatory Simplification and Abstraction of Results. The recurring feedback that results were "too much technique" or required "simple and easy to understand materials" highlights a failure to adequately simplify complex data. The lesson is not only about what is presented, but how. Future projects must enforce the creation of a "Tool/Result Abstraction Layer"—a dedicated component within the Knowledge Hub that presents the key output metrics (e.g., Soil Health Index, Carbon Sequestration Potential) using only visual indicators (e.g., traffic light system: Green/Good, Yellow/Caution, Red/Action Required) and clear, non-technical language. This ensures accessibility for users with limited time or technical education, significantly broadening the potential user base beyond academics and specialized consultants.

Lessons Learned in Methodology and Systemic Barrier Mitigation

The Pareto Chart analysis (Figure 3), which aggregated qualitative feedback across all events, clearly demonstrated that Financial Constraints/Profitability and Policy/Governance Gaps were the overwhelming and most frequently cited systemic barriers. The most important lesson learned from this convergence is that the project's technical solutions (DSTs, SHEM models) cannot exist in an economic or regulatory vacuum; they must be actively and overtly integrated with strategies to overcome these external, non-technical constraints.

The Local Contextualization Imperative

The most successful events (measured by private sector engagement and high relevance scores for operational tools) were those that were deeply rooted in the local agricultural context. The Spanish events and the German events, both showing high private sector attendance, successfully framed the project results around specific local crops, regional economic challenges, and relevant local agricultural policy. The core lesson here is that the consortium's central technical team should act as content providers, but the local partner must have the autonomy and responsibility to radically localize the presentation. This includes adapting visual materials, translating case studies to local farm types (e.g., replacing a Bulgarian case study with an Andalusian olive grove case study), and tailoring the discussion to the regional regulatory nuances. The project should not aim for perfect uniformity in presentation, but for maximum relevance in delivery. The constraint of language (requiring all presentations to be given in the local language, as was the case) is only the first step; true contextualization requires cultural and agronomic adaptation.

First Recommendation: Establishing a 'Local Adaptation Budget Contingency'. A small, flexible budget must be allocated to each local partner

specifically for adaptation purposes—e.g., hiring a local graphic designer to rapidly create localized infographics, contracting a local farmer to present their own data using the tool, or purchasing refreshments that align with local customs. This small investment reinforces the perception that the project is addressing local problems with locally relevant solutions, rather than imposing a pan-European technical solution.

Second Recommendation: Fostering Peer-to-Peer Learning over Expert Lecture. The most valuable interactions noted were those that facilitated direct dialogue between stakeholders, rather than a top-down presentation of results. Future event methodologies must enforce a shift from 'presentation mode' to 'workshop/discussion mode', minimizing formal presentations to 20-25% of the total event time. The remainder should be dedicated to structured breakout sessions where stakeholders use the tools collaboratively, facilitated by the local partner. This ensures that the primary knowledge transfer mechanism is one of peer-to-peer validation and collaborative problem-solving, which significantly accelerates trust and adoption among the private sector.

7 Conclusions

The NOVASOIL project, through its rigorous multi-actor engagement strategy encapsulated by the second round of Multiplier Events (MEs) and targeted Spanish stakeholder interviews, has achieved its primary objectives of disseminating project results, validating the utility of its tools, and, most critically, gaining a deep, cross-European understanding of the systemic barriers to soil health adoption. This concluding section synthesizes the key achievements, discusses the verified utility of the project's outputs, and outlines the strategic implications for future research and policy efforts under the EU Soil Health Mission.

The successful execution of the dissemination methodology across seven diverse European countries (as documented in the national reports) confirms the viability of a large-scale, multi-partner approach to knowledge transfer. The project successfully transitioned from merely presenting scientific findings to engaging in structured, two-way dialogue with end-users, policy makers, and researchers.

One of NOVASOIL's most significant achievements lies in its demonstrated ability to bridge both geographic and sectoral divides. The cross-event analysis revealed stark differences in stakeholder profiles—from the research-dominated discourse in Bulgaria and Italy to the pragmatic, private-sector focus in the Netherlands and Spain. This heterogeneity, while presenting a dissemination challenge, simultaneously validated the project's core hypothesis: that the effective scaling of soil health solutions requires context-specific adaptation.

The data confirms that the most successful engagement occurred when the local partners acted as cultural and technical translators, tailoring the presentation of the Decision Support Tool (DST) and the Knowledge Hub to regional farming practices (e.g., olive groves in Spain, fruit and vegetables in France, extensive farming in Germany). This adaptation, often mandated by the local language requirement, proved essential for achieving the observed high relevance scores from end-users, particularly for the operational DST. The project did not just transfer knowledge; it validated the process of localized, culturally competent knowledge transfer.

The core of the NOVASOIL exploitable results is the integrated Tool-Box, comprising the DST, the Soil Health Economic Model (SHEM), the Policy Briefs, and the Knowledge Hub. The stakeholder feedback provided a clear verdict on the perceived utility of these components:

- **Operational Tools (DST):** Consistently rated highly by the private sector and farmers, demonstrating a strong perceived utility for day-to-day farm management and input optimisation. The DST's focus on actionable, on-farm recommendations (e.g., in the face of climate change challenges noted in the Spanish interviews) resonated directly with the operational imperatives of profitability and sustainability. Its value lies in providing a data-driven basis for adopting soil health practices.
- **Strategic Tools (Policy Briefs, SHEM Insights):** These elements demonstrated high relevance among the Public/Policy and Research segments. The high scores in countries like Estonia, France, and Italy underscore the immediate demand for evidence-based analysis to inform the rapidly evolving EU legislative landscape, particularly concerning the forthcoming Soil Health Law and the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). These tools are instrumental for actors focused on systemic change and regulatory coherence.

The conclusion here is that the project successfully developed a **Dual-Purpose Solution Set**, simultaneously addressing the **micro-level needs** of the farmer (via the DST) and the **macro-level needs** of the policy maker (via the Policy Briefs), validating the consortium's multi-disciplinary approach.

The most frequently cited thematic challenge across all events was Financial Constraints / Profitability. This finding transcends national borders and crop types, confirming a fundamental market failure: the current structure of agricultural value chains and policy incentives does not adequately reward or de-risk the transition to soil-health-improving practices.

Stakeholders consistently highlighted the high initial costs, the prolonged return-on-investment horizon, and the risk associated with adopting non-conventional techniques. For example, Spanish farmers specifically pointed to the difficulties in rentability for rainfed agriculture and the foreseen cuts in CAP subsidies as critical disincentives.

The second most frequently cited barrier was Policy/Governance Gaps. This refers not just to the absence of supportive legislation, but to the complexity, incoherence, and frequent changes within existing regulatory frameworks (e.g., CAP).

Feedback indicated a need for greater clarity and stability in long-term incentives. The current policy environment is often perceived as uncertain or even contradictory, discouraging the long-term investment required for true soil regeneration. For the policy-focused stakeholders, the high relevance rating of the Policy Briefs confirms that they are actively seeking evidence-based pathways to resolve this systemic incoherence. The NOVASOIL consortium concludes that successful implementation of the DST's recommendations hinges on the parallel creation of an enabling policy environment that offers predictable, long-term rewards for ecosystem service delivery, reinforcing the "public goods" aspect of soil health.

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Annex. Guideline

NOVASOIL

INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH

Grant agreement ID: 101091268

Multiplier event guideline

The objective of this multiplier event, unlike the initial ones organized at the beginning of the project, is to present the project's results firsthand. This way, during the event's development, it will serve to increase the impact of the project's results, but also to determine if the sector's needs and demands are being met, allowing for the identification of required next steps and specific activities or sectors.

The aim of this multiplier event, unlike the earlier ones organized at the start of the project, is to directly showcase the project's results. By doing so, the event will not only boost the impact of the project's outcomes but also help us understand if the sector's needs and demands are being met. This will, in turn, allow us to identify what further steps are necessary and in which specific activities or sectors.

This event is open to the general public, with a clear focus on land managers, farmers, policy-makers, NGOs, researchers, and, of course, investors, all falling under the same stakeholder categories.

All project partners are contributing to this task, meaning a multiplier event must be organized in each consortium country. We expect to reach a minimum attendance of 10 people at each. The one exception is AREFLH (BEN8); due to their corporate structure, their event will be entirely online and will include participants from various countries.

With the same flexibility granted at the project's outset, we recommend that the event doesn't last longer than 3 hours. This allows us to prioritize presenting the results and discussing them with the audience.

The event should kick off with a brief overview of the project and its objectives, serving as a reminder, and then primarily focus on the following key results:

- **Preliminary DCE Results:** During the Ferrara plenary session, DCE managers presented preliminary results from various case studies. Depending on your audience's interests, you can concentrate on a specific type or country, or discuss them more broadly. Remember to briefly mention the methodology used.

- **Toolbox Prototypes:** We currently have three digital tools within the toolbox. These can be demonstrated and evaluated with the audience, letting them actively participate in understanding how they work. This information is incredibly valuable for identifying areas that need strengthening, and we can include these insights in our conclusions to guide future developments or benefit sister projects.
- **Policy Implications:** The NOVASOIL project has assessed the main policies related to soil health, and several policy briefs have been published on this topic. The key conclusions reached can be a great starting point for discussion during your event. You might want to prepare a template with these main conclusions to facilitate an open discussion with your audience.

Recommendations

If you want to promote discussion and interaction, try to provide your audience with the main questions that will be addressed beforehand, if possible. There are various tools, both digital and paper-based, to help you do this. You could use a platform like Miro, or simply gather comments on paper with sticky notes, similar to how it was done during the participatory activity organized by UNIFE at the plenary session here in Seville.

If your event has more than 20 people, consider forming small groups of 6-7 individuals, each with a moderator to facilitate discussion. Have each group summarize their main conclusions and then present them to the other groups.

Remember, we're nearing the end of the project, so now is a great time to encourage attendees to follow the project on social media if they haven't already. Create a hashtag for the event! The EVENOR communication team can offer support with this.

There are also platforms promoted by the European Commission that communicate and disseminate these kinds of events. This could be a good tool to use if you anticipate a smaller audience, though having 10-15 people from various categories should be sufficient.

Within this document, you'll find the agenda template and the report that needs to be shared with the coordination team. Please remember that personal data should not be shared, and all personal information must be anonymized.

P.S. Don't forget to take photos! It's always nice to have that kind of material for the final reports.

Report

Organising Partner:

Venue:

Time:

Time	Activity
xx-xx	- Registration
xx-xx	- Welcome and introduction – organization
xx-xx	- Presentation of the project – organization
xx-xx	- Discussion: Key Questions
xx-xx	- Evaluation and Feedback
xx-xx	- Conclusions and wrap up

QUESTIONS AND COMMENTS

This section is to note all interesting discussion, comments and feedback received by stakeholders during the event.

This will feed the Report for Deliverable 5.4

To steer the direction of discussion:

1. To what extent do the project results presented today address the current needs and demands within your sector or area of work? (Please use a scale of 1-5, where 1 = Not at all, and 5 = Very much so.)
2. Which specific project results or tools (e.g., DCE insights, toolbox prototypes, policy briefs) do you find most relevant and applicable to your professional activities? Why?
3. Were the project results presented in a way that was clear, understandable, and actionable for you?
4. Do you foresee any specific challenges or opportunities in applying these project results within your own context? If so, please elaborate.
5. Based on today's event, what further steps or information would help you better utilize the project's outcomes to address your specific needs?

